

Chemistry of Thorium. Part V. An Electrometric Study on the Quantitative Precipitation of Thorium as Normal Tellurite

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The results of a series of conductometric titrations of thorium (IV) against potassium tellurite with an overall concentration of 30-40% ethanol have been reported; the possibility of carrying out direct as well as reverse titrations over a satisfactory range of thorium concentration is thereby concluded and the effect of ethanol concentration has also been studied which under cited conditions lends support to the formation of thorium tellurite (molar ratio of Th:Te being 1:2).

Borzolius, Ramelsberg, Lenher, and Wolsensky, and others¹ studied the preparation and properties of tellurites of Li, NH_4^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Cu^{2+} , Ag^+ , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Hg^+ , Pb^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Yt^{4+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zr^{4+} , Th^{4+} and UO_2^{2+} .

Very recently conductometric determination of barium as normal tellurite² has been studied in this laboratory. The work is now extended to the application of TeO_3^{2-} in conductometric determination of thorium. The present communication thus reports the results of a series of conductometric titrations of thorium with potassium tellurite in detail under varied experimental conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium tellurite was prepared by dissolving the B. D. H. reagent grade sample in conductivity water and tellurium estimated as TeO_2 by the usual gravimetric method³. Thorium nitrate solution was similarly prepared by dissolving 'Pure Quality' of Riedel-make sample and thorium was estimated as ThO_2 by the oxalate method⁴, the respective molar concentration of the two solutions being 0.09392 *M* and 0.1100 *M*. Different volumes of 0.1100 *M*- $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ solution were made to 65 ml and direct conductometric titrations were carried out at 0.0003385 *M*, 0.0005078 *M*, 0.000677 *M*, 0.0008464 *M*, 0.001016 *M*, and 0.001185 *M* concentrations of thorium against 0.09392 *M*- K_2TeO_3 . In reverse titrations, different volumes of 0.09392 *M*- K_2TeO_3 solution were made to 65 ml and these solutions at 0.001156 *M*, 0.001445 *M*, and 0.001733 *M* concentration titrated against 0.1100 *M*- $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ solution. While studying the effect of ethanol, 65 ml of 0.0006708 *M*- $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ solution containing 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50% ethanol was titrated against 0.09392 *M*- K_2TeO_3 .

Mullard conductivity bridge, type E7566, a 220-volt, A. C. line-operated, direct reading electronic instrument with electron-beam indicator for the balance was used for measure-

1. Mellor, "A Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1954, Vol XI, p. 77.
2. This *Journal*, 1962, **39**, 84.
3. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1955, pp. 442-443.
4. *Ibid.*, p. 473.

ments of conductance. The readings were recorded in mhos at 50 cycles. The dip-cellof the type E7591 with platinised bright platinum electrodes and a 10-ml microburette were connected to the terminal cell on the meter, the main switch was turned on, and the selector switch to mhos for recording the conductance directly. The instrument was set to the zero loss angle for highest sensitivity. The range switch was switched to the expected range and the pointer knob rotated till the electron-beam indicator showed the maximum shadow angle. The scale value was recorded and multiplied by the factor indicated on the range-selector switch to find the conductance directly.

Direct Conductometric Titrations.—A known volume of thorium nitrate solution with an overall 30-40% EtOH was taken in the cell, placed on magnetic stirrer, the dip-cell was properly dipped in solution, and the initial conductance recorded. Potassium tellurite solution was added from a microburette in small amounts to the thorium nitrate solution, the mixture stirred well, and the reading recorded after allowing the precipitate to settle.

FIG. 1. Direct conductometric titration.

The temperature was maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ by circulating a current of water from a constant temperature water bath in jacket provided with the reaction vessel (cell) for the purpose. The conductances were plotted against the volumes of the titrant. The results are embodied in Figs. 1 and 2 (curves I-VI).

FIG. 2. Direct conductometric titration.

Reverse Conductometric Titrations.—In this set, a known volume of potassium tellurite containing the above mentioned percentage of ethyl alcohol was taken in the reaction vessel (cell) and thorium nitrate solution added from the microburette. Other procedures were the same as in the direct titration. The results are reported in Fig. 3 (curves I-III).

Effect of Ethanol at Different Concentrations.—In the course of this observation it was noted that in aqueous medium the curve was neither smooth nor the break was sharp, which ultimately led to no well-defined end-point; hence the necessity of the addition of ethanol arose and observations were recorded at various ethanolic concentrations among which 30-40% range was found to be the best. The results obtained are recorded in Fig 4 (curves I-VI).

DISCUSSION

The reaction with the present titration of thorium with potassium tellurite may be represented as

The unsuitability of the purely aqueous medium for the quantitative and complete precipitation of thorium as normal tellurite may be explained on the assumption that the dissolution

K-felbarita soln. (ml).

FIG. 4. Effect of ethanol.

Thorium nitrate soln. (ml).

FIG. 3. Reverse conductometric titration.

and hydrolysis of the precipitate starts in solution which is remedied by the addition of 30-40% ethanol to a remarkable extent.

Breaks, obtained in direct as well as reverse titrations, correspond to the molar ratio of 1:2 for thorium and tellurium. Under the conditions cited above, the formation of normal thorium tellurite seems to be only possible.

Thus the present method is an easy and accurate titrimetric procedure for micro-determination of thorium.

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